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STUDYING THE WORKS OF ENGLISH WRITERS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE LESSONS

***Annotation.** The use of authentic texts, including fiction, in teaching English as a foreign language is becoming increasingly widespread, especially in Europe and Asia. In particular, it is explained by the growing popularity of communicative teaching methods and the gradual abandonment of the teacher-centered system of teaching a foreign language. In connection with the use of authentic texts in English lessons, the question arises about the criteria for selecting such texts and about the most effective methods of working with them in the classroom. In Russian education, including in the teaching of foreign languages, significant changes have recently occurred, while the use of literary texts in foreign language education has a long tradition here, however, specific empirical information that would allow us to analyze the approaches of Russian English teachers to the use of literary texts in teaching is clearly insufficient. Russian and English teachers took part in a survey on the criteria for selecting literary texts for use in English lessons and methods of working with these texts. It has been established that the literary texts preferred by teachers and the techniques used to work with them in the classroom are very similar to those that were popular during the Soviet Union. At the same time, modern teachers take into account the interests of their students to a greater extent when selecting texts and focus their attention when teaching English on improving communication skills.*

***Keywords:** linguistics, English language, teaching English, fiction in foreign language education, pedagogy, reading.*

Modern research focuses primarily on the analysis of the use of literary texts in the practice of specific foreign language teachers or on the theoretical foundations of the use of original literary works in teaching a foreign language. However, there is no data on how today's practice of using literary texts in Russian schools differs from the Soviet period. Meanwhile, the use of authentic literary works for teaching a foreign language has a long history in Russia, although perhaps not all former schoolchildren recall their experience of such learning with pleasure.

In recent years, several publications have appeared devoted to the experience of using the language approach in teaching English in Russian universities. For example, S. Pitina found that the teachers surveyed were satisfied

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with the results of the discourse methodology as a variant of the language approach to teaching English using literary texts. In their opinion, this technique is effective for the development of all basic language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening, since it involves the study of authentic samples of spoken and written discourse. T. Bekisheva and G. Gasparyan showed that at Tomsk Polytechnic University teachers use literary works in teaching students English and using methods such as writing essays on the works they read, summarizing the text and role-playing. The cultural approach is considered the most traditional in the study of literary works [Lazar, 1993]. When using it, in contrast to the language approach, the student receives information about the historical and socio-political conditions in which the text was written, studies ideological trends and special cultures reflected in the text, learns details about the life of the writer, about contemporary literary movements and directions of philosophical and religious quests. As part of the cultural approach to the study of literary works, methods such as a story about the biography of the author, about the main periods of his work, and an explanation of the main features of the literary movement to which the work belongs are used. Students are shown a portrait of the author, photographs of people or places that inspired the writer. recommends using a cultural approach in teaching English. She gives preference to poetic works, including sonnets by W. Shakespeare, and introduces students to the history of the creation of the work and the era in which it was written. Not all researchers consider the cultural approach to the study of literary works effective in the practice of teaching a foreign language. With this approach, the focus of the lesson shifts from the student to the teacher and little time is devoted to language practice. Nevertheless, English teachers continue to use this approach Teachers who took part in S. Ainy's study, for example, justified their preferences by the fact that by applying a cultural approach, it is possible to achieve a better understanding of the text by students.

Methodology. Based on the observation method (systematization of personal experience in teaching English and English-language literature and the experience of the leadership of the Higher Educational Institutions on the relevant topics); methods of analysis and synthesis aimed at integrating literary, linguistic and methodological approaches to the study of literary text; a modeling method associated with the construction of an algorithm for performing complex SRC.

Results. Development of an algorithm for the examination of an authentic foreign language work of art for the possibility of its use in teaching a foreign language. At the same time, the identification of the methodological potential of the text is carried out at the extralinguistic, artistic and linguistic levels of the text. The analysis of each of these levels is aimed at establishing a correspondence between the specific features of the text and the types of tasks or forms of work applicable within the framework of communicative classes, the purpose of which is teaching reading.

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Thus, modern methodological research emphasizes the importance of including literary texts in a foreign language teaching program as authentic material that develops critical thinking and communicative competence: a) in the humanitarian aspect, related to the moral, emotional, intellectual and creative spheres through the correlation of the described topics and characters and events with personal experience; b) in the linguistic aspect, associated with the formation of skills in four types of speech activity, expanding knowledge of authentic lexical and grammatical material and means of expression presented in significant contexts. Moreover, researchers have noted the positive impact of lessons based on literary works on students' attitudes towards a foreign language as a subject [11, p. 43], experimentally proves the effectiveness of developing reading and critical thinking skills based on the material of fiction texts based. At the same time, these advantages can turn into difficulties, which often prevent the use of fiction in foreign language lessons due to complexity, "non-standard", non-conventionality both at the linguistic (lexical-grammatical) level and at the content-related level. with the ability to interpret culturally, socially, historically determined meanings in combination with individual author's codes and symbols. In addition, difficulties are caused by the volume of the text and the correspondence of the text to the gender and age interests of students. Another problem is related to the ability to integrate literary texts into the curriculum in such a way that they are organically integrated into the basic educational and methodological complex (EMC), taking into account all the above-mentioned features. Conclusion

The work is based on the assertion that the effective use of a work of art for teaching a foreign language is possible only on the basis of an integrated approach to the text as a source of linguistic, literary, sociocultural, and historical information. The algorithm for the methodological examination of a literary text, presented in our article, was developed on the basis of literary and methodological research by domestic and foreign scientists and specialists in teaching English, as well as our own experience in teaching English language and literature and management.

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